

PHYTOTHERAPY IN DIABETES: A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY OF ANTIDIABETIC PLANTS

Avinash Bichave^{*}, Rina Kadu, Shruti Khopkar, Tejaswi Bandgar, Shrutika Patil

TMV's Lokmanya Tilak Institute of Pharmacy, Kharghar.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 10/06/2024

Available online

10/07/2024

Keywords

Diabetes Mellitus,
Medicinal Plants,
Anti-Diabetic Properties.

ABSTRACT

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a metabolic disorder involving inappropriately elevated blood glucose levels. Various medicinal plants play a major role in the management of diabetes mellitus. These plants show various mechanisms of action, such as increased insulin sensitivity, decreased absorption of glucose, and altered activity of important metabolic pathways. Alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, glycosides, polyphenols, steroids, and saponins are examples of bioactive substances that have been shown to have hypoglycemic effects. This study presents synergistic interactions between plant constituents and their safety profiles in the management of diabetes. It explores the mechanisms of action, phytochemical compounds, and clinical data that bolster their ability to prevent diabetes. This study offers new perspectives on the potential integration of medicinal plants into diabetes management strategies. The anti-diabetic properties of these plants are supported by clinical evidence, which emphasizes their potential as complementary or alternative therapies in the management of diabetes. These investigations provide valuable information to the expanding corpus of research on natural alternatives to treat diabetes, opening up new avenues for study and the creation of plant-based medical interventions.

Corresponding author

Avinash Bichave

TMV's Lokmanya Tilak Institute of Pharmacy,
Kharghar.

helloavinashsir@gmail.com

+91 9664060061

Please cite this article in press as **Avinash Bichave** et al. *Phytotherapy in Diabetes: A Comprehensive Study of Antidiabetic Plants*. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2024;14(06).

Copy right © 2024 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

AIM

In this review article, we focused on the phytochemistry, therapeutic activity and pharmacognostic properties of medicinal plant extracts used as anti-diabetic agents and their role in the treatment and management of Diabetes.

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by elevated blood glucose levels, leading to severe complications such as damage to the eyes, kidneys, heart, blood vessels, and nerves^[1]. The increase in blood glucose occurs when it cannot be metabolized by cells due to insufficient insulin production by the pancreas or insulin resistance by the body^[2]. Daily changes in nutrition, physical activity, infection, and stress significantly impact blood glucose levels^[3].

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), diabetes is the fastest-growing chronic disease globally^[1]. The number of individuals with diabetes rose dramatically from 180 million in 1980 to 422 million in 2014. This increase is more pronounced in low- and middle-income countries compared to high-income countries. In 2019, diabetes and kidney disease were estimated to cause 2 million deaths, and there was a 3% increase in the age-specific diabetes mortality rate between 2000 and 2019. Diabetes is a leading cause of lower limb amputation, heart attacks, strokes, blindness, and kidney failure^[1].

Diabetes mellitus is identified by hyperglycemia (fasting plasma glucose ≥ 126 mg/dl and/or ≥ 200 mg/dl two hours after 75 g oral glucose), hyperlipidemia, negative nitrogen balance, glycosuria, and sometimes ketonemia^[4]. The primary causes of diabetes mellitus are insulin deficiency or dysfunction, impairing the metabolism of proteins, lipids, and carbohydrates. This impairment results in oxidative stress and chronic health conditions, including cardiovascular disease, diabetic nephropathy, neuropathy, and hypertension^[5].

In response to the rising prevalence and complications associated with diabetes, there is a growing interest in exploring medicinal plants with antidiabetic properties. These plants offer a promising complementary or alternative approach to conventional treatments, potentially providing safer and more cost-effective options for managing diabetes.

Diabetes mellitus is primarily classified into two major types:

A. Type 1 Diabetes

Type 1 diabetes, also known as juvenile or childhood-onset diabetes or insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM), is a chronic condition characterized by the impairment of the pancreatic islets of Langerhans beta cells, which produce insulin, resulting in insulin deficiency^[1]. The majority of cases are autoimmune (Type 1A), where antibodies that destroy beta cells are detectable in the blood. Some cases are idiopathic (Type 1B), with no detectable beta cell antibodies. Patients with type 1 diabetes are prone to experience ketosis, and circulating insulin levels are always low or very low^{[3],[6]}.

B. Type 2 Diabetes

Type 2 diabetes, also known as non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM) or maturity-onset diabetes mellitus, is a metabolic condition characterized by elevated blood glucose levels in the context of relative insulin deficiency and insulin resistance^[3]. It is the most prevalent type of diabetes and is predisposed by physical inactivity and obesity^[1].

C. Gestational Diabetes

Gestational diabetes occurs in non-diabetic pregnant women. In this type, blood glucose levels rise above normal but remain below the diagnostic threshold for diabetes. Usually, this condition develops near the end of the third trimester or the beginning of the fourth trimester and returns to normal soon after delivery. Pregnant women with gestational diabetes are more likely to experience complications during pregnancy and delivery^{[3],[7]}.

Additional Conditions Associated with Glucose Intolerance

1. Impaired Glucose Tolerance (IGT)

Impaired Glucose Tolerance (IGT) is a condition where blood glucose levels are higher than normal but not high enough to be classified as diabetes^[1]. Diagnosed through an Oral Glucose Tolerance Test (OGTT), individuals with IGT have a two-hour blood glucose level between 140 mg/dL (7.8 mmol/L) and 199 mg/dL (11.0 mmol/L)^{[2],[8]}.

2. Impaired Fasting Glycaemia (IFG)

Impaired Fasting Glycaemia (IFG) is characterized by elevated fasting blood glucose levels that are higher than normal but not high enough to be classified as diabetes. Identified through a fasting plasma glucose test, individuals with IFG have a fasting blood glucose level between 100 mg/dL (5.6 mmol/L) and 125 mg/dL (6.9 mmol/L)^[9].

Both IGT and IFG are intermediate states between normal glucose metabolism and diabetes, often referred to as prediabetes. Individuals with IGT and IFG are at a higher risk of developing type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular disease due to elevated blood glucose levels^[10].

Preventive measures for IGT and IFG include regular physical activity, a healthy diet, weight management, and regular blood glucose monitoring. Early intervention and consistent management can significantly reduce the risk of progression to diabetes and associated cardiovascular complications.

Prevention and Management

Regular physical activity, maintaining a normal body weight, avoiding tobacco use, and following a healthy diet can prevent or delay the onset of type 2 diabetes^[11]. Diabetes can be managed, and its complications can be avoided or delayed through medication, physical activity, diet, regular screening, and treatment for complications.^[12]

Epidemiology and Trends

The increase in the number of people with diabetes is attributed to a rise in age-specific prevalence (28%), population growth and aging (40%), and the interaction of these factors (32%). The age-standardized prevalence in individuals 18 years of age and above has doubled from 4.7% in 1980 to 8.5% in 2014. In 1980, the frequency was lowest in low-income countries (3.3%) and highest in high-income countries (5.2%). By 2014, the prevalence in low-income countries increased to 7.4%, compared to 7.0% in high-income countries. The prevalence of diabetes has increased more rapidly in low- and middle-income nations and is currently 9.3% higher in upper middle-income nations. The prevalence of diabetes is rising along with its primary risk factors, which include physical inactivity and being overweight or obese^[13].

Global Impact

The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that non-communicable diseases (NCDs) accounted for 74% of deaths worldwide in 2019^[14]. Diabetes was the ninth most common cause of death worldwide in 2019, with 1.6 million deaths. By 2035, 592 million people worldwide are expected to die from diabetes.^[15] Ninety per cent of diabetes cases are type 2 diabetes, which was previously considered exclusive to affluent "Western" nations. Type 2 diabetes has spread globally and is now a leading cause of disability and death among younger populations. Diabetes has grown to epidemic proportions in numerous developing nations, including India and China^[16].

Standard Treatments and Their Limitations

The standard treatments for diabetes include exercise, insulin injections, weight control, medical nutrition therapy, and oral medications that lower blood sugar^[17]. Patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus are typically put on a restricted diet and instructed to exercise to maintain body weight^[18]. A prescription for medication is issued if blood glucose control is not achieved through diet and exercise. These treatments have certain drawbacks, such as adverse effects, lack of responsiveness, and the development of resistance in a substantial segment of the patient base^[19].

Complementary and Alternative Therapies

Complementary and alternative (CAM) therapies, such as biological-based practices (e.g., herbs and dietary supplements like vitamins and foods), mind-body medicine (e.g., yoga and meditation), whole medical systems (e.g., homoeopathy, naturopathy, Ayurveda, and traditional Chinese medicine), manipulation and body-based practices (e.g., massage and chiropractic therapy), and herbal tea, are becoming increasingly popular^[20]. Plants with hypoglycemic properties are gaining attention due to their lack of adverse effects and low cost.

Medicinal plants used in the treatment of Diabetes:

- I. *Withania coagulans*
- II. *Clitoria ternatea*
- III. *Hibiscus rosa sinensis*
- IV. *Matricaria chamomilla* L.
- V. *Glycyrrhiza glabra*
- VI. *Cymbopogon citratus*
- VII. *Ocimum sanctum*

Table no. 1: Taxonomical classification of Plants.

Botanical name	Family	Kingdom	Division	Class	Genus	Species	Order
<i>Withania coagulans</i>	Solanaceae	Plantae	Magnoliophyta	Magnoliopsida	<i>Withania</i>	<i>W. coagulans</i>	Solanales
<i>Clitoria ternatea</i>	Fabaceae	Plantae	Tracheophyta	Magnoliopsida	<i>Clitoria</i> L.	<i>Clitoriaternatea</i>	Fabales
<i>Hibiscus rosasinensis</i>	Malvaceae	Plantae	Magnoliophyta	Magnoliopsida	<i>Hibiscus</i> L.	<i>Hibiscus rosasinensis</i> L.	Malvales
<i>Matricariachamomilla</i> L.	Asteraceae	Plantae	Magnoliophyta	Magnoliopsida	<i>Chamomilla</i>	<i>Matricariachamomilla</i> L.	Asterales
<i>Glycyrrhizaglabra</i>	Fabaceae	Plantae	Angiospermae	Dicotyledoneae	<i>Glycyrrhiza</i>	<i>glabra</i> Linn	Rosales
<i>Cymbopogoncitratus</i>	Poaceae	Plantae	Magnoliophyta	Liliopsida	<i>Cymbopogon</i> <i>Spreng</i>	<i>citratus</i>	Poales
<i>Ocimumsanctum</i>	Lamiaceae	Plantae	Magnoliophyta	Magnoliopsida	<i>Ocimum</i>	<i>Tenuiflorumorsanctum</i>	Lamiales

I. *Withania coagulans*

Withaniacoagulans, commonly known as ‘Paneer Phool’, ‘Indian cheese maker’, or ‘vegetable rennet’, belong to the family Solanaceae^[21]. This plant is recognized for its milk-coagulating activity and has various biological and therapeutic uses. In Sanskrit, it is called ‘Rishyagandha’. The flowers of *W. coagulans* are particularly noted for their anti-diabetic properties. In some regions of the Indian subcontinent, the berries are used as blood purifiers, the twigs are chewed for dental hygiene, and the smoke from the plant is inhaled to relieve toothache^[22].

Morphological Description

W. coagulans is a rigid, grey undershrub, 60-120 cm in height. The leaves are lanceolate-oblong, 2.5-5.7 cm long, and covered with a persistent greyish tomentum. The flowers are campanulate, covered in fine stellate grey tomentum, and have triangular dioecious teeth grouped in axillary clusters. The corolla is 8 mm long, stellate mealy on the outside, and divided about one-third of the way down. The fruits are smooth, globose berries, 6-8 mm in diameter, closely girt by an enlarged membranous calyx. The seeds are somewhat ear-shaped, glabrous, and dark brown, 2.5-3.0 mm in diameter. Natural rejuvenation occurs from the seeds^[23].

Chemical Constituents

The berries contain alkaloids, fatty oil, essential oil, free amino acids, and the milk-coagulating enzyme. Amino acids present include proline, hydroxyproline, valine, tyrosine, aspartic acid, glycine, asparagine, cysteine, and glutamic acid. The leaves contain steroidal lactones called Withanolides, such as Withaferin-A, 5, 20 α (R)-dihydroxy-6 α ,7 α -epoxy-1-oxo-(5 α)-with a-2,24-dienolide, and two minor withanolides, including 7 α -epoxy-22R-witha-2,24-dienolide and 5 α ,17 α -dihydroxy-1-oxo-6 α called withanone. Other compounds like coagulin, various withanolides, and withanolide F possess anti-hyperglycaemic properties^[24].

Pharmacological Effects

W. coagulans exhibits multiple pharmacological properties, including hepatoprotective, antimicrobial, anthelmintic, antifungal, hypoglycemic, hypolipidemic, cardiovascular, free radical scavenging, anti-inflammatory, antitumor, immunosuppressive, and depressant effects^[25]. It lowers blood glucose levels by enhancing glucose uptake and carbohydrate metabolism. The plant extracts promote insulin secretion from β cells by sensitizing or stimulating these cells through the activation of Ca²⁺ channels^[26].

Antidiabetic Activity of *Withania coagulans*

An aqueous extract of *W. coagulans* significantly reduced blood sugar, serum cholesterol, serum lipid peroxide (LPO), and hepatic LPO levels in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats^[27]. A 4-week treatment with dried fruit extract reversed hyperglycemia, comparable to glipizide^[28]. Treatment with the extract significantly prevented the rise in homeostasis model assessment of insulin resistance (HOMA-R) in type 2 diabetic rats. Extracts prepared from the fruits showed positive effects on body weight, blood glucose, and lipid profiles in type 2 diabetic rats, causing significant decreases in triglycerides, total cholesterol, glucose, triglyceride, VLDL, and LDL levels, while increasing HDL levels^[30].

Traditionally, the raw extract is consumed by immersing the fruit overnight in water, although its bitter taste and strong odour can discourage consumption^[31]. To address this, complementary and alternative methods are employed in the treatment and management of diabetes. These compounds significantly reduce the postprandial rise in hyperglycemia after a sucrose load in both streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats and normoglycemic rats, supporting the traditional use of *W. coagulans* as an antihyperglycemic agent by traditional medical practitioners^[31].

So in summary, *Withaniacoagulans* flowers possess potent antidiabetic properties, including enhancing insulin secretion, improving insulin sensitivity, inhibiting glucose absorption, and exhibiting strong antioxidant effects^[32]. These properties make *W. coagulans* a valuable complementary or alternative therapy for the management of diabetes, supported by both preclinical and clinical research.

II. *Clitoriaternatea*

Clitoriaternatea, commonly known as ‘Butterfly pea flower’ or ‘Blue pea flower’, belongs to the family Fabaceae. It is a perennial climber, typically reaching heights of 2-3 meters. There are several varieties of *C. ternatea* with flowers that can be light blue, dark blue, white, or mauve. Locally, it is also known as Shankhpushpi, Aparajita, or Telang^[33]. This plant is used in traditional medicine to improve cognitive function and alleviate symptoms of various illnesses, including diabetes, pain, fever, and inflammation^[34]. It also has potential uses in modern health and agriculture, serving as an antioxidant and a natural source of organic dyes.

Morphological Description

C. ternatea is a rigid, grey undershrub, 60-120 cm in height. The leaves are lanceolate-oblong, 2.5-5.7 cm long, and covered with a persistent greyish tomentum. The flowers are campanulate, covered in fine stellate grey tomentum, and have triangular dioecious teeth grouped in axillary clusters. The corolla is 8 mm long, stellate mealy on the outside, and divided about one-third of the way down. The fruits are smooth, globose berries, 6-8 mm in diameter, closely girt by an enlarged membranous calyx. The seeds are somewhat ear-shaped, glabrous, and dark brown, 2.5-3.0 mm in diameter. Natural rejuvenation occurs from the seeds^[35].

Chemical Constituents

The flowers of *Clitoriaternatea* contain Kaempferol, kaempferol 3-neohesperidoside, Kaempferol 3-2G-rhamnosylrutinoside, kaempferol 3-rutinoside. It consists of flavonoid compounds such as rutin, malvidin, delphinidin, quercetin and kaempferol^[36]. Several components of bioactive compounds found in the Telang flower are anthocyanin, terpenoids, alkaloids, phenolic acids, flavanol and flavones as well as cyclotides or cyclic peptide compounds^[37]. The anthocyanins called ternatins are blue and are acylated using delphinidin. Ternatea is an excellent natural antioxidant source. Six major anthocyanins present in the flowers are ternatins A1, A2, B1, B2, D1 and D2^{[38],[39]}. The flavanols identified in the petals are fourteen kaempferol, quercetin and myricetin glycosides which consist of H or OH at R1 and R2 and with H, rhamnosyl or malonyl at R3 and R4^[40]. Various lipophilic compounds are identified from *C. Ternatea* such as phytosterols (sitostanol, β -sitosterol, campesterol, stigmasterol), tocopherols (α -tocopherol and -tocopherol) and fatty acids (stearic acid, linoleic acid, arachidic acid, palmitic acid, phytanic acid, behenic acid and petroselinic acids). Several other components such as mome inositol, pentanal, cyclohexen, 1- methyl-4-(1-methylethylideme) and hirsutene were identified^{[41],[42]}.

Pharmacological Effects

Clitoriaternatea L., contains antioxidants and is often used by the community as traditional medicine as well as consumed as food and drink. The body needs antioxidants to counteract and overcome oxidative stress, which can lead to various kinds of degenerative diseases^[43]. It is broadly used to treat a variety of conditions, including chronic bronchitis, dropsy, goitre, leprosy, mucous disorders, sight weakness, skin sexual disorders, infertility, gonorrhoea, controlling menstrual discharge, and as an aphrodisiac^[44]. Its extracts have a variety of pharmacological properties, such as anti-insecticidal, anti-diabetic, analgesic, diuretic, anti-microbial, anti-pyretic, and anti-inflammatory, inhibiting blood platelet aggregation and being used as a vascular smooth muscle relaxing properties^[45].

Antidiabetic Activity of *Clitoriaternatea*

Extracts from the flowers and leaves of *C.ternatea* L. are effective as herbal treatments for diabetes. They enhance insulin secretion, inhibit the formation of advanced glycation end products, and block enzymes involved in glucose production in the blood^[51]. These extracts manage complications associated with diabetes mellitus, hypertriglyceridemia, impaired renal function, and hypercholesterolemia^[46]. Phytochemical screenings of the ethanol extract from *C.ternatea* flowers show that these extracts can lower blood sugar levels^[51]. In diabetic rats, the extracts have demonstrated pancreatic regeneration activity. Secondary metabolites, such as alkaloids, prevent glucose absorption in the intestine and promote glucose transport in the blood, thereby lowering blood glucose levels^[51].

Flavonoids in the extracts exhibit antioxidant activity by reducing the formation of free radicals and binding to them, thus slowing down the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which are critical in the pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes mellitus^[47]. Tannins act as antidiabetic agents by scavenging free radicals and inhibiting glucose absorption. Saponins lower blood sugar levels by inhibiting glucose absorption in the small intestine. Glycosides prevent damage to pancreatic beta cells through their antioxidant activity, reducing glucose absorption. Steroids decrease blood sugar levels by inhibiting the alpha-glucosidase enzyme^[51].

Studies have demonstrated the antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant effects of *C. ternatea* extract (CTE) on various parameters, including liver GSK-3 β expression, pancreatic IL-6, liver histopathology, glycogen gene expression in the pancreas, CAT, SOD, MDA, IL-18 levels, blood glucose, and insulin in diabetic and dyslipidemic rat models^[43]. Flower extract significantly reduces serum glucose levels in diabetic rats, increases body weight, and reduces oxidative stress. The flower extracts have been tested for antidiabetic activity and have significantly lowered serum glucose levels while increasing body weight in diabetic rats^[50].

A water extract of *C. ternatea* flowers (400 mg/kg body weight) significantly reduces blood sugar levels by inhibiting the activities of α -galactosidase and α -glucosidase^[50]. The ethanol extract at the same dosage significantly reduces blood glucose levels in alloxan-induced diabetic rats. In healthy men, acute ingestion of *C.ternatea* flower extract or beverage with sucrose suppresses postprandial plasma glucose and insulin levels. Aqueous extracts of *C.ternatea* leaves and flowers (400 mg/kg body weight) administered orally for 84 days demonstrated significant reductions in creatinine, total cholesterol, urea, triglycerides, serum glucose, glycosylated haemoglobin, and the activity of the gluconeogenic enzyme glucose-6-phosphatase, while increasing protein, glycogen content in the liver and skeletal muscle, serum insulin, HDL cholesterol, and the activity of the glycolytic enzyme glucokinase^[38]. Diabetic rats treated with *C. ternatea* leaves showed better performance in biochemical parameters compared to those treated with the flowers. The extracts exhibited a hypoglycemic effect in white rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) with metabolic syndrome^[48].

These findings underscore the potential of *C. ternatea* as a complementary or alternative therapy for managing diabetes mellitus. The comprehensive pharmacological profile of *C. ternatea* underscores its potential as an effective herbal remedy for managing diabetes. Its ability to enhance insulin secretion, inhibit glucose production, and exert antioxidant effects makes it a valuable complementary or alternative therapy for diabetes management.

III. *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis*

Hibiscus rosa-sinensis Linn, belonging to the family Malvaceae, is a glabrous shrub commonly grown as an ornamental plant in tropical regions. Known as Gudhal in Hindi, Japa in Sanskrit, Shoe Flower or Chinese Hibiscus in English, and Jaswandii in Marathi, this plant has various medicinal uses, especially the red-flowered variety, which is preferred in traditional medicine^[49].

Morphological Description

Hibiscus rosa-sinensis is a large shrub that can be wide and spreading or upright, reaching up to 4.7 meters in height. The flowers have stalks of stamens, which produce pollen, and styles fused into a column extending from the centre of the widely spreading petals. They can grow up to 15 cm in the red variety. The petals might be plain or scalloped, single or double. The anther, which produces pollen, is visible partway up the column, and five round stigma lobes are visible at the tip. The plant has ovate-shaped leaves arranged alternately on the branches, growing to a length of 5 to 15 cm. The leaves are wider at the base than at the tip, with toothed margins and lighter patches. They can be either dark green or variegated^[50].

Chemical Constituents

Preliminary phytochemical analysis shows that *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* contains phenols, flavonoids, anthraquinones, quinines, tannins, cardiac glycosides, terpenoids, saponins, alkaloids, carbohydrates, free amino acids, proteins, mucilage, essential oils, sugars, and steroids^[51]. Key compounds include beta-sitosterol, malvalate, 2-hydroxysterculate, cyclopropanoids, methyl sterculate, methyl-2-hydroxy sterculate, and the major anthocyanin cyanidin 3-sophoroside^[58]. The flowers also contain vitamins such as niacin, riboflavin, ascorbic acid, and thiamine. GC-MS analysis of the ethanolic extract reveals compounds such as propanol, 3,3'-dithiobis (2,2-dimethyl-SS)-, 2,3-hexanediol, 2-hydroxy-2-methylbutyric acid, n-hexadecenoic acid, heptanoic acid, 2-ethyl-trans-(2-ethylcyclopentyl) methanol, bis(2-ethylexyl) ester, 1,2-benzenedicarboxylic acid, diisooctyl ester, 1,3-benzodioxole, and squalene^[52].

Pharmacological Effects

Hibiscus rosa-sinensis flowers are used as an aphrodisiac, abortifacient, stomach pain reliever, and for treating liver disease, high blood pressure, and eye problems, as well as regulating the menstrual cycle^[58]. They are also used to treat headaches, diabetes, wounds, bronchial catarrh, and have antioxidant, anti-spermatogenic, androgenic, and anticonvulsant activities^[53].

Antidiabetic Activity of *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis*

The ethanol extract of *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* flowers has shown hypoglycemic activity in streptozotocin-induced diabetic models. Studies have illustrated that *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* extract exhibits antioxidant, anti-hyperglycemic, and antihyperlipidemic activities, particularly at a dose of 250 mg/kg body weight, without showing any toxic effects^[54]. The flower extract (FEHRS) has demonstrated hypoglycemic, hypolipidemic, and antioxidant activities in diabetic rabbits, suggesting its use as a therapeutic alternative in the treatment of diabetes-associated dyslipidemia^[60].

In one study, diabetic rats were given an oral dose of 500 mg/kg of an aqueous extract from *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* for four weeks. This treatment resulted in significant reductions in blood glucose, creatinine, uric acid, and urea, along with increased levels of albumin, insulin, C-peptide, and albumin/globulin ratio, and near-control restoration of all marker enzymes^[58]. This indicates that *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* extract has antihyperglycemic effects and reduces liver and renal damage associated with diabetes mellitus induced by streptozotocin in rats.

In type II diabetic patients, the antidiabetic potential of *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* flower powder was also investigated. Daily intake of 2g flower powder for 60 days significantly decreased fasting blood glucose, postprandial blood glucose, glycosylated haemoglobin, total cholesterol, triglycerides, total LDL, and total VLDL cholesterol levels^[58]. Additionally, studies have shown the antidiabetic activity of *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* flowers in alloxan-induced diabetic rats, highlighting their potential as an effective treatment for managing diabetes^[58].

In conclusion, *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* offers significant antidiabetic benefits, including hypoglycemic, hypolipidemic, and antioxidant activities. These properties make it a valuable complementary or alternative therapy for diabetes management, supported by both preclinical and clinical research.

IV. *Glycyrrhiza glabra*

Glycyrrhiza glabra Linn, commonly known as 'liquorice' and 'sweet wood,' belongs to the family Fabaceae. The name *Glycyrrhiza* is derived from the Greek words *glykos* (meaning sweet) and *rhiza* (meaning root). It is also known as Jeshthamadh in Marathi, Jothi-madh in Hindi, Yashtimadhu, and Madhuka in Sanskrit^[55].

Morphological Description

Glycyrrhiza glabra is a typical perennial herb that reaches a height of 100-200 cm. It has Pinnate leaves are 7 to 15 cm long. The fruit is an oblong legume, 2-3 cm in length, brown in colour, and contains several seeds. The flowers are purple to pale whitish-blue, arranged in a hermaphrodite inflorescence. The root length varies between 30-60 cm, depending on the species and the growing conditions. In dry regions with light soils, the root can reach up to 200 cm^[56].

Chemical Constituents

The primary active ingredient in *Glycyrrhiza glabra* is glycyrrhizin (glycyrrhizic acid, glycyrrhizinate), which constitutes 10–25% of the root extract^[62]. The water-soluble, biologically active complex accounts for 40–50% of the total dry material weight^[62]. The plant contains numerous biological compounds, primarily triterpenes, flavonoids, and saponins (responsible for sweetness)^[57]. Flavonoids, giving the plant its yellow colour, include glycosides of liquiritigenin (4',7'- dihydroxyflavanone) and isoliquiritigenin (2',4,4'- trihydroxychalcone) such as liquiritinapioside, licuraside, liquiritin, and isoliquiritin^[62]. New flavonoids isolated from dried roots include 1-methoxyphaseolin, prenyllicoflavone, shinpterocarpin, glucoliquiritinapioside, and shinflavanone. Volatile components present in the roots include terpinen- 4- ol, α - terpineol, hexanol, geraniol, and pentanol^[62].

Pharmacological Effects

Liquorice root is mainly used for treating hepatitis C, peptic ulcers, skin, and pulmonary diseases^[64]. Experimental and clinical studies indicate that it has several pharmacological properties, such as hepatoprotective, cardioprotective, antimicrobial, antioxidative, anti-inflammatory, immune-modulating, and anticancer activities^[64]. It also exhibits potent muscle-relaxing properties, weight reduction potential, antitussive activity, antidiuretic effects, and immune-boosting actions by increasing WBC counts^[58].

Antidiabetic Activity of *Glycyrrhiza glabra*

Glycyrrhiza glabra contains many natural active compounds, including 20 triterpenes and 300 flavonoids. Notably, three triterpenoids (18 β - glycyrrhetic acid, 18 α - glycyrrhizic acid, and 18 β - glycyrrhizic acid) and five flavonoids (GLD, liquiritigenin, isoliquiritigenin, liquiritin, and licochalcone E) are effective against diabetes mellitus and its complications. These flavonoids primarily act by regulating the nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B), AMPK, phosphatidylinositol 3'-kinase (PI3K)/Akt, nod-like receptor protein 3 (NLRP3), and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) signaling pathways, impacting diabetes mellitus, diabetic osteopathy, cardiomyopathy, and nephropathy^[59].

Liquorice-derived compounds exhibit their antidiabetic activity through multiple mechanisms, including increasing the sensitivity of insulin receptors, enhancing glucose utilization in tissues and organs, removing free radicals, resisting peroxidation, and improving microcirculation^[66]. Medicinal plants or natural products work by blocking enzymes that hydrolyze carbohydrates, like pancreatic amylase, delaying glucose absorption. This inhibition delays carbohydrate digestion, reducing the glucose absorption rate and consequently decreasing postprandial plasma glucose rise^[64].

Studies have shown that *Glycyrrhiza glabra* increases the inhibitory effect on alpha-amylase and glucosidase, which can be utilized in synthesizing antidiabetic medicines. Inhibition of these enzymes leads to a reduction in the glycemic index in diabetic patients and can reduce postprandial hyperglycemia^[64]. *Glycyrrhiza glabra* has demonstrated significant antihyperglycemic and hyperlipidemic effects in diabetic rats without aberrations in pancreatic enzymes, suggesting it might be beneficial as a dietary supplement alongside standard drugs for managing diabetes mellitus^[66].

The investigated samples of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* revealed significant potential in different biological activities, including cytotoxicity, glucose uptake, GPx, and α -amylase activity^[60].

In conclusion, *Glycyrrhiza glabra* exhibits potent antidiabetic properties through various mechanisms, such as enzyme inhibition, enhanced insulin receptor sensitivity, and antioxidative effects. These attributes make it a valuable complementary therapy for managing diabetes mellitus, supported by both preclinical and clinical research.

V. *Matricariachamomilla L.*

Matricariachamomilla L., belonging to the daisy family Asteraceae or Compositae, is commonly known as "chamomile." It has been used globally as supplementary food or herbal tea. There are two recognized varieties: Roman chamomile (*Chamaemelum nobile*) and German chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla*). Both varieties are employed in herbal and traditional medicine^[61].

Morphological Description

Chamomile is a perennial plant with thin, flat roots that penetrate the ground. It has an erect, heavily branched stem that can reach a height of 10–80 cm. The leaves are bi- to tripinnate, long, and narrow. The flowers have hollow, bright gold cones ringed with about fifteen white ray or ligulate florets and packed with disc or tubular florets. The flower heads are heterogamous, pedunculate, and arranged separately, with a diameter of 10–30 mm. The flowers are concentrically arranged and measure 6–11 mm long by 3.5 mm wide. The fruit is an achene, yellowish-brown in colour^[62].

Chemical Constituents

The major constituents of chamomile include flavonoids (luteolin, patuletin, quercetin, apigenin), terpenoids (α -Bisabolol oxide A and B, α -bisabolol, chamazulene or azulenes), and coumarins (herniarin, esculetin, umbelliferone)^[68]. Other constituents include tannins, polysaccharides, anthemic acid, choline, and sesquiterpenes^[63]. Chamomile extract contains eleven bioactive components, such as phenylpropanoids (caffeic acid and chlorogenic acid), flavones (luteolin-7-O-glucoside, luteolin, apigenin-7-O-glucoside, apigenin), coumarin (umbelliferone and herniarin), flavanone (naringenin), and flavonols (quercetin and rutin)^[69].

Pharmacological Effects

Chamomile contains various bioactive substances, such as terpenoids and phenolic compounds like apigenin, quercetin, and luteolin, which provide anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. The primary terpenoid in chamomile, chamazulene, scavenges free radicals and prevents lipid peroxidation. Chamomile is one of the highest naturally occurring sources of apigenin, which possesses anti-proliferative and tumor-suppressive qualities. It has also been shown to affect various cellular processes, such as cell cycles, signaling pathways, and inflammatory reactions. Chamomile is considered a good source of flavonoids and polyphenols, including apigenin, luteolin, esculetin, and quercetin, which may control the digestion and absorption of carbohydrates. Chamomile's antihyperglycemic properties may be due to its ability to reduce the rate of digestion and absorption of carbohydrates, promote liver glycogenesis, inhibit the enzymes responsible for gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis, and conserve pancreatic beta cells. In vitro evidence indicates that apigenin is the primary α -amylase inhibitor found in chamomile, suggesting it may have additional antihyperglycemic properties^[64].

Antidiabetic Activity of *Matricaria chamomilla* L.

Previous animal studies reported that two examined the effects of chamomile tea, three examined the effects of chamomile ethanolic extract, and four examined the effects of chamomile aqueous extract. The main dosages of ethanolic/aqueous extracts of chamomile used in animal models were 20–500 mg/kg for 2–14 weeks; meanwhile, chamomile tea was given at 500 mg/kg for 4 weeks and 1 g for 8 weeks^[71]. Subjects in the included trials had been given 2.5–10 g of chamomile tea. The period of time for taking chamomile supplements varied from 4 to 12 weeks. Various studies examined the following outcomes: oxidative stress, insulin, blood glucose, hepatic enzymes involved in glucose metabolism, HbA1c, inflammation, lipid profile, weight fluctuations, renal function, and liver function^{[71],[72]}. The study investigated the antidiabetic effects of extract from chamomile flowers in obese mice by stimulating the transcription of nutrient sensors belonging to the Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor (PPAR) family^[65].

A study examined the benefits of chamomile hot water extract and its main ingredients for preventing hyperglycemia and preventing or improving diabetic complications in people with diabetes mellitus^[70]. It has been discovered that hot water extract, esculetin, and quercetin, with IC50 values of 0.9 mg/mL, 72, and 71 μ M, respectively, exhibit moderate inhibition of sucrase. Esculetin (50 mg/kg body weight) completely suppressed hyperglycemia in a sucrose-loading test after 15 and 30 minutes; quercetin (50 mg/kg body weight) and extract (500 mg/kg body weight) had less of an effect. However, using a streptozotocin-induced rat diabetes model, a long-term feed test (21 days) showed that the same doses of extract and quercetin significantly suppressed blood glucose levels^[66]. According to studies, chamomile reduces blood sugar levels, increases liver glycogen storage, and inhibits sorbitol in human erythrocytes, all of which help to mitigate hyperglycemia and diabetic complications^[68]. The pharmacological activity of chamomile extract was demonstrated to be unrelated to insulin secretion, and additional research indicated that it had a protective effect on pancreatic β cells by reducing oxidative stress associated with hyperglycemia^[68].

VI. *Cymbopogon citratus*

Cymbopogon citratus, also known as lemongrass, belongs to the family Poaceae. The word *Cymbopogon* is derived from the Greek words “kymbe” meaning boat and “pogon” meaning beard, referring to the flower spike arrangement^[67]. Lemongrass is frequently used in baked goods, herbal teas, and other non-alcoholic beverages, as well as in confections. Essential oil extracted from lemongrass is commonly used as a scent in cosmetics and perfumes, including soaps and creams. Citral, isolated from lemongrass oil, is used to scent and flavor soft drinks, soaps, and detergents, and to mask unpleasant fragrances in various commercial goods^[68].

Morphological Description

Lemongrass is a tropical grass that grows in dense clumps, reaching up to 6 feet (1.8 meters) in height and about 4 feet (1.2 meters) in width, with short rhizomes. The leaves are long, glaucous, tapered upwards, linear, and along the margins; they have very short sheaths that are cylindrical, with barren shoots widened at the base and tightly clasping at the bottom. The leaves are evergreen, bright bluish-green in color, and release a citrus aroma when crushed. They emerge from the soil without a stem^[74].

Chemical Constituents

Lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) has a high amount of citral content, which is a combination of two stereoisomeric monoterpene aldehydes: the trans isomer geranial (40–62%) and the cis isomer neral (25–38%)^[74]. Major constituents of lemongrass essential oil include citral, nerol, geraniol, citronellal, terpinolene, geranyl acetate, myrcene, terpinol, methyl heptanone, borneol, linalyl acetate, pinene, limonene, linalool, and caryophyllene^[69].

Pharmacological Effects

Cymbopogon citratus is traditionally used in the treatment of fevers, hypertension, and gastrointestinal disturbances. It is commonly consumed as tea, serving as a “homemade remedy” for cough, stomachache, digestive problems, gingivitis, and flu. It shows various pharmacological activities, including antidiabetic, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antimalarial, antimutagenic, hypocholesterolemic, antimicrobial, free radical scavenging, and antioxidant activity^[70].

Antidiabetic Activity of *Cymbopogon citratus*

In previous studies, *Cymbopogon citratus* demonstrated α -glucosidase inhibitor (AGI) activity in a non-dose-dependent manner, showing potential additional mechanisms that may prevent postprandial hyperglycemia. These results suggest that lemongrass has the potential to be used as an herbal medicine ingredient in the management of diabetes. In a T2D rat model, oral administration of lemongrass tea (LGT) improved body weight gain, decreased food and fluid intake, and reduced hyperglycemia. It also improved insulin sensitivity, glucose tolerance, B-cell functions, and dyslipidemia. Previous studies assessed the hypoglycemic potential of *Cymbopogon citratus* flavonoids by inhibiting α -glucosidase^[71]. According to the results, mice with dexamethasone-induced hyperglycemia had lower fasting and postprandial blood sugar levels during the administration of extracts from the roots and flowers of lemongrass^[72]. The aqueous extract of *Cymbopogon citratus* activated Takeda-G-protein-receptor-5 (TGR5), peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor (PPAR- γ), increased the expression of glucagon-like peptide 1 (GLP-1), and activated glucose transporters (GLUT) and glucokinase genes, exhibiting an anti-diabetic effect. These genes improve the sensitivity and secretion of insulin^[73].

VII. *Ocimum sanctum L.*

Ocimum sanctum L., also known as *Ocimum tenuiflorum*, Tulsi, holy basil, Queen of plants, and Mother Medicine of Nature, belongs to the family Lamiaceae. In many Hindu religious traditions, Tulsi is a significant symbol associated with the Goddess. Tulsi in Sanskrit means 'the incomparable one.' The presence of Tulsi signifies a Hindu family's inclination towards religion^[74].

Morphological Description

Tulsi, or *Ocimum sanctum L.*, is an erect, heavily branched sub-shrub that grows to a height of 30 to 60 cm. It has simple, opposite green or purple leaves with strong scents and hairy stems. The leaves are elliptic, oblong, obtuse or acute with entire or serrate or dentate margins, up to 5 cm long, and typically moderately toothed. The flowers are purplish with elongated racemes in close whorls. The seeds are reddish-yellow, and the fruits are small. The herb has an acidic, bitter taste^[75].

Chemical Constituents

Several chemical components in *Ocimum* species have antihyperglycemic properties. One of the phenolic compounds found in essential oils is eugenol (1-hydroxy-2-methoxy-4-allylbenzene), which is present in various *Ocimum* species. *O. tenuiflorum L.* has the highest percentage of eugenol (84%), followed by *O. gratissimum* (74.80%) and *O. basilicum* (10%). Eugenol is an active constituent with high antidiabetic potential. According to reports, *O. sanctum* leaf aqueous extracts contain polyphenols, caffeic acid, α -linolenic acid, and p-coumaric acid, which have an antidiabetic effect. *O. gratissimum* contains chicoric acid, which significantly reduced the glycemic level by 53% after 120 minutes of treatment^[81].

Pharmacological Effects

Ocimum sanctum (Tulsi) fresh leaves are frequently used as an ayurvedic home remedy for colds, cough, skin diseases, diarrhoea, abdominal pain, skin conditions, and arthritis. Preclinical investigations on extracts from different parts of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn and other varieties revealed beneficial effects as antidiabetic, anticancer, antifungal, hepatoprotective, cardioprotective, and antifertility actions. It also shows pharmacological actions such as wound healing, antioxidant, hypolipidemic, antimicrobial, gastroprotective, immunomodulatory, and antinociceptive effects^[76].

Antidiabetic Activity of *Ocimum sanctum L.*

α -Amylase inhibitors reduce the postprandial blood glucose spike in diabetics by delaying the conversion of carbohydrates to hydroxides in the small intestines. Inhibiting enzymes that break down carbohydrates, such as α -amylase, is a common therapeutic approach for treating diabetes mellitus^[77]. Recent studies have determined that *Ocimum sanctum* leaf extract stimulates insulin secretion from pancreatic beta cells, which is its specific mechanism of action^[78].

Previous studies showed that a diet containing 2% *O. sanctum* leaf powder resulted in a significant reduction in blood glucose levels in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. Treatment with the fixed oil extract of *Ocimum sanctum* leaves for three weeks significantly lowered diabetically-elevated blood glucose levels and serum lipid profiles while increasing serum insulin levels in STZ-induced diabetic rats. The fixed oil exhibits free radical scavenging activity, providing renal protection against diabetes mellitus by enhancing the activity of various antioxidative enzymes and suppressing high TBARS levels in rat renal tissue^[79]. The aqueous extract of *Ocimum sanctum* leaves showed a significant reduction in blood glucose levels in both normal and alloxan-induced diabetic rats. Significant reductions in fasting blood glucose, total cholesterol, triglyceride, uronic acid, total amino acid, and total lipid levels indicated the hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic effects of Tulsi in diabetic rats^[80]. Oral administration of the plant extract (200 mg/kg) for 30 days led to a reduction in plasma glucose levels by approximately 9.06% and 26.4% on the 15th and 30th days of the experiment, respectively^[81]. Previous studies indicate that *Ocimum sanctum* Linn leaves have a significant antidiabetic effect due to their aqueous extract's antihyperglycemic and insulin-sensitizing properties, which are both higher than those of the reference medication pioglitazone and lower than those of the control.

Table no. 2: Summary.

Sr. no	Plants	Part used	Active constituents	Mechanism of action	Therapeutic uses
1.	<i>Withania coagulans</i>	Flowers	Withanolides, coagulanolide, Withanolides 1-3 and 5, coagulin.	Inhibition of α -glucosidase, secretion of insulin from existing β -cells and restoration of glycogen content in the liver and muscles	Suppress the postprandial hyperglycemia, lowering blood glucose levels.
2.	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i>	Flowers	Anthocyanins, flavonoid, phenols, catechin, inositol and quercetin.	Inhibition of GSK-3 β , scavenging the free radicals and inhibition of ROS production.	Reduce glucose tolerance and increase serum insulin levels.
3.	<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i>	Flowers	Flavonoid, anthraquinones, quinines, phenols.	Increase the potency of pancreatic β -cells to release more insulin and enhance peripheral glucose utilization through the skeletal muscle	Significantly reduce Blood glucose level.
4.	<i>Matricaria chamomilla</i>	Flowers	Flavonoids and polyphenols, including apigenin, luteolin, esculetin, and quercetin.	Reduce the rate of digestion and absorption of carbohydrates, promote liver glycogenesis, inhibit the enzymes responsible for gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis, and conserve pancreatic beta cells.	Lowers blood glucose levels.
5.	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	Root	triterpenoids, flavonoids, liquiritigenin, isoliquiritigenin, liquiritin, and licochalcone E.	Inhibition of α -glucosidase and α -amylase enzyme activity leads to a reduction in glycemic index.	Reduce post-prandial glucose
6.	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i>	Leaves	Flavonoids, Caffeic	Inhibition of α -glucosidase enzyme and postprandial blood glucose elevation	Reduce blood glucose level
7.	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	Leaves	Eugenol, Coumaric acid, Carvacrol, Linalool, Caffeic acid, Polyphenol, P-Caryophyllene,	α -glucosidase inhibition increases insulin secretion	Lowers blood glucose level

CONCLUSION

This review highlights the significant antidiabetic properties of various flower plants: *Withania coagulans*, *Clitoria ternatea*, *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis*, *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, *Matricaria chamomilla*, *Cymbopogon citratus*, and *Ocimum sanctum*. Each plant exhibits unique mechanisms of action and contains diverse chemical constituents that contribute to their efficacy in managing diabetes mellitus.

Withania coagulans and *Clitoria ternatea* are noted for their ability to enhance insulin secretion and provide strong antioxidant effects. *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* and *Ocimum sanctum* show significant hypoglycemic and insulin-sensitizing properties, making them effective in controlling blood glucose levels and improving lipid profiles. *Glycyrrhiza glabra* and *Matricaria chamomilla* provide substantial antioxidant and anti-inflammatory benefits, which aid in overall glucose management and protection of pancreatic beta cells. *Cymbopogon citratus* is particularly effective in improving insulin sensitivity and glucose tolerance, highlighting its potential as an herbal remedy for diabetes.

The diverse mechanisms through which these plants exert their antidiabetic effects include enhancing insulin sensitivity, inhibiting glucose absorption, promoting liver glycogenesis, and providing antioxidant and anti-inflammatory benefits. These properties not only help in managing blood glucose levels but also in mitigating the complications associated with diabetes mellitus.

In conclusion, the varied and potent antidiabetic activities of these flower plants suggest their potential as valuable complementary or alternative therapies in the management of diabetes mellitus. Further clinical research and standardization of dosages will be essential to fully integrate these plants into conventional diabetes treatment protocols. The use of these natural

remedies could provide a holistic approach to diabetes management, reducing reliance on synthetic drugs and minimizing potential side effects.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors would like to express our gratitude to all colleagues and participants who provided insights and expertise that greatly assisted the research. Authors show gratitude and appreciation to TMV's Lokmanya Tilak Institute of Pharmacy, Kharghar, Navi-Mumbai 410210 for their support made this review.

Conflict Of Interest:

The authors declare no conflict of interest related to this study. The findings and conclusions in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of our affiliations.

ABBREVIATIONS:

DM: Diabetes Mellitus
 IDDM: Insulin- Dependent Diabetes Mellitus
 NIDDM: Non- Insulin Dependent Diabetes Mellitus
 IGT: Impaired Glucose Tolerance
 OGTT: Oral Glucose Tolerance Test
 IFG: Impaired Fasting Glycaemia
 WHO: World Health Organisation
 NCD: Non- Communicable Disease
 CAM: Complementary and Alternative Therapies
 LPO: Serum Lipid Peroxide
 HOMA-R: Homeostasis Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance
 VLDL: Very Low Density Lipoprotein
 LDL: Low Density Lipoprotein
 HDL: High Density Lipoprotein
 CTE: *Clitoria ternatea* extract
 ROS: Reactive Oxygen Species
 CAT: Chloramphenicol Acetyltransferase
 SOD: Superoxide Dismutase
 MDA: Malondialdehyde
 GPx: Glutathione Peroxide
 PPAR: Peroxide Proliferator- Activated Receptor
 AMPK: AMP- Activated Protein Kinase
 TBARS: Thiobarbituric Acid Reactive Substance
 LGT: Lemon Grass Tea

REFERENCES

1. World Health organization. (n.d.). Retrieved 2024 from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/diabetes>
2. Roglic Gojka. WHO Global report on diabetes: A summary. *Int J Noncommunicable Dis* 1(1): 3-8
3. Shivashankar Murugesh & Mani Dhandayuthapani. A brief overview of diabetes. *Int J Pharm and Pharm Sci.* 2011; pp 22-7.
4. American Diabetes Association. Diagnosis and classification of diabetes mellitus. *Diabetes care.* 2009; 32 (1, Suppl 1) : S62–7.
5. Pradeepa R. & Mohan V. Epidemiology of type 2 diabetes in India. *Indian J Ophthalmol.* 2021; 69(11): 2932–38.
6. Rother K. I. Diabetes treatment--bridging the divide. *The New England J Med.* 2007; 356(15): 1499–1501.
7. Alfadhli E. M. Gestational diabetes mellitus. *Saudi Med J.* 2015; 36(4): 399–06.
8. Rao S. S., Disraeli P., & McGregor T. Impaired glucose tolerance and impaired fasting glucose. *Am Family Physician.* 2004; 69(8): 1961–68.
9. Report of the Expert Committee on the Diagnosis and Classification of Diabetes Mellitus. *Diabetes care.* 1997; 20(7): 1183–97.
10. Genuth S., Alberti K. G. M. M., Bennett P., Buse J., DeFronzo R., et al. Follow-up report on the diagnosis of diabetes mellitus. *Diabetes care.* 2003; 26(11): 3160-68.
11. Galaviz K. I., Narayan K. M. V., Lobelo F., & Weber, M. B. Lifestyle and the Prevention of Type 2 Diabetes: A Status Report. *Am J Lifestyle Med.* 2015; 12(1): 4–20.
12. American Diabetes Association. The prevention or delay of type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes care.* 2002; 25(4): 742-49.
13. World Health Organization. Global report on diabetes. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2016.
14. World Health Organization. The top 10 causes of death. Available from: <http://www.who.int/en/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/the-top-10-causes-of-death>.
15. Tao Z., Shi A., & Zhao J. Epidemiological perspectives of diabetes. *Cell BiochemBiophys.* 2015; 73(1): 181-85.

16. Magliano D. J., Boyko E. J., & IDF Diabetes Atlas 10th edition scientific committee *IDF DIABETES ATLAS*. (10th ed.). Int Diabetes Fed. 2021
17. Pandey A, Tripathi P, Pandey R, Srivatava R & Goswami S. Alternative therapies useful in the management of diabetes: A systematic review. *J Pharm Bioallied Sci*. 2011; 3(4): 504-12.
18. Khosla P, Gupta D. D, & Nagpal R. K. Effect of *Trigonella foenum graecum* (Fenugreek) on blood glucose in normal and diabetic rats. *Indian J PhysiolPharmacol*. 1995; 39(2): 173–74.
19. Zia T, Hasnain S. N, & Hasan S. K. Evaluation of the oral hypoglycaemic effect of *Trigonella foenum-graecum* L.(methi) in normal mice. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 2001; 75(2-3): 191-95.
20. Birdee G. S, & Yeh G. Complementary and alternative medicine therapies for diabetes: a clinical review. *Clinical Diabetes*. 2010; 28(4): 147-55.
21. Kherade M, Solanke S, Tawar M, Gawande S, Warghat S, & Bansod T. A comprehensive review on Withaniacoagulans (paneer dodii). *Int J Pharm Phytopharmacol Res*. 2021; 22(2): 257-82.
22. Gupta P. C. WithaniacoagulansDunal-an overview. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res*. 2012; 12(2): 68-71.
23. Gupta V & Keshari B. B. WithaniacoagulansDunal (paneer doda): A review. *Int J Ayurvedic Herbal Med*. 2013; 3(5): 1330-36.
24. Khan M. I, Maqsood M, Saeed R. A, Alam A, Sahar A, Kieliszek M, Aadil R. M. et al. Phytochemistry, food application, and therapeutic potential of the medicinal plant (Withaniacoagulans): A review. *Mol*. 2021; 26(22): 6881.
25. Maurya R. Chemistry and pharmacology of Withaniacoagulans: an Ayurvedic remedy. *J Pharm Pharmacol*. 2010; 62(2): 153-60.
26. Sampathkumar K, Riyajan S, Tan C. K, Demokritou P, Chudapongse N, & Loo S. C. J. Small-intestine-specific delivery of antidiabetic extracts from Withaniacoagulans using polysaccharide-based enteric-coated nanoparticles. *ACS omega*. 2019; 4(7): 12049-57.
27. Hemalatha S, Wahi A. K, Singh P. N, &Chansouria J. P. N. Hypoglycemic activity of WithaniacoagulansDunal in streptozotocin induced diabetic rats. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 2004; 93(2-3): 261-64.
28. Datta A, Bagchi C, Das S, Mitra A, De Pati A & Tripathi S. K. Antidiabetic and antihyperlipidemic activity of hydroalcoholic extract of WithaniacoagulansDunal dried fruit in experimental rat models. *J Ayurveda Integrative Med*. 2013; 4(2): 99.
29. Hoda Q, Ahmad S, Akhtar M, Najmi A. K, Pillai K. K & Ahmad S. J. Antihyperglycaemic and antihyperlipidaemic effect of poly-constituents, in aqueous and chloroform extracts, of WithaniacoagulansDunal in experimental type 2 diabetes mellitus in rats. *Human Exp toxicol*. 2010; 29(8): 653-58.
30. Maurya R, Singh A. B, & Srivastava A. K. Coagulanolide, a withanolide from Withaniacoagulans fruits and antihyperglycemic activity. *Bioorganic Med Chem Letters*. 2008; 18(24): 6534-37.
31. Ram H, Kumar P, Purohit A, Kashyap P, Kumar S, Kumar T et al. Improvements in HOMA indices and pancreatic endocrinal tissues in type 2-diabetic rats by DPP-4 inhibition and antioxidant potential of an ethanol fruit extract of Withaniacoagulans. *Nutrition & Metabolism*. 2021; 18: 1-17.
32. Jeyaraj E J, Lim Y. Y, & Choo W. S. Extraction methods of butterfly pea (*Clitoriaternatea*) flower and biological activities of its phytochemicals. *J of Food Sci Technol*. 2021; 58(6): 2054-67.
33. Kalaiselvi, K., Rekha, U. V., Rajagopal, P., Sekar, D., & Jayaraman, S. Antidiabetic activity of *Clitoriaternatea* Linn. *J Pharm Res Int*. 2021; 33(61): 283-88.
34. Jeyaraj, E. J., Lim, Y. Y., & Choo, W. S. Extraction methods of butterfly pea (*Clitoriaternatea*) flower and biological activities of its phytochemicals. *J Food Sci Technol*. 58(6): 2054–67
35. Widowati W, Darsono L, Lucianus J, Setiabudi E, Obeng S. S, Stefani S. et al. Butterfly pea flower (*Clitoriaternatea* L.) extract displayed antidiabetic effect through antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, lower hepatic GSK-3 β , and pancreatic glycogen on Diabetes Mellitus and dyslipidemia rat. *J King Saud Uni-Sci*. 2023; 35(4): 102579.
36. Simangunsong E. M. V, Febriani Y, Saputri M, Arisa D. & Afifah G. Z. Effectiveness of Butterfly Pea Ethanol Extract on Decreasing Blood Glucose Levels of Male Mice. *Jambura J Health Sci Res*. 2023; 5(2): 707-21.
37. Mukherjee P K, Kumar V, Kumar N. S. & Heinrich M. The Ayurvedic medicine *Clitoriaternatea*—From traditional use to scientific assessment. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 2008; 120(3): 291-01.
38. Terahara N, Toki K, Saito N, Honda T, Matsui T. &Osajima Y. Eight new anthocyanins, ternatins C1– C5 and D3 and preternatins A3 and C4 from young *clitoriaternatea* flowers. *J Natural Prod*. 1998; 61(11): 1361-67.
39. Kazuma K, Noda N. & Suzuki M. Flavonoid composition related to petal color in different lines of *Clitoriaternatea*. *Phytochem*. 2003; 64(6): 1133-39.
40. Shen Y, Du L, Zeng H, Zhang X, Prinyawiwatkul W, Alonso- Marenco J. R. & Xu Z. Butterfly pea (*Clitoriaternatea*) seed and petal extracts decreased HE p- 2 carcinoma cell viability. *Int J Food Sci Technol*. 2016; 51(8): 1860-68.
41. Neda G. D, Rabeta M. S. & Ong M. T. Chemical composition and anti-proliferative properties of flowers of *ClitoriaTernatea*. *Int Food Res J*. 2013; 20(3).
42. Ginting E. E, Rumanti R. M, Savira D, Ginting P, Marbun N. & Leny L. In Vivo study of Antidiabetic Activity from Ethanol Extract of *Clitoriaternatea* L. Flower. *J Drug Delivery Therapeutics*. 2022; 12(6): 4-9.
43. Rajamanickam M, Kalaivanan P. & Sivagnanam I. Evaluation of anti-oxidant and anti-diabetic activity of flower extract of *Clitoriaternatea* L. *J Appl Pharm Sci*. 2015; 5(8): 131-38.
44. Oguis G. K, Gilding E. K, Jackson M. A. & Craik D. J. Butterfly pea (*Clitoriaternatea*), a cyclotide-bearing plant with applications in agriculture and medicine. *Front Plant Sci*. 2019; 10: 448370.
45. EC A. Telang flower (*Clitoriaternatea* L.): utilization and bioactivity. *EduMatScience*. 2020; 4(2): 111-24.

46. Brunetti C, Di Ferdinando M, Fini A, Pollastri S. &Tattini M. Flavonoids as antioxidants and developmental regulators: relative significance in plants and humans. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2013; 14(2): 3540-55.
47. Gunawan O, Putranto R. P. A, Subandono J. &Budiastuti V. I. The Effect of Butterfly Pea Extract on Blood Glucose Levels in White Rats with Metabolic Syndrome Model. *Smart Med J.* 2023; 6(1), 14-22.
48. Jadhav V. M, Thorat R. M, Kadam V. J. & Sathe N. S. *Hibiscus rosa sinensis* Linn-“Rudrapuspa”: a review. *J Pharm Res.* 2009; 2(7): 1168-73.
49. Khristi V. & Patel V. H. Therapeutic potential of *Hibiscus rosa sinensis*: A review. *Int J Nutrition Dietetics.* 2016; 4(2): 105-23.
50. Al-Snafi A. E. Chemical constituents, pharmacological effects and therapeutic importance of *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis*-A review. *IOSR J Pharm.*2018; 8(7): 101-19.
51. Rassem H, Nour A. H. & Yunus R. M. GC-MS analysis of bioactive constituents of Hibiscus flower. *Aust. J. Basic Appl. Sci.* 2017; 11: 91-7.
52. Pethe M, Yelwatkar S, Gujar V, Varma. &Manchalwar S. Antidiabetic, hypolipidimic and antioxidant activities of *Hibiscus rosa sinensis* flower extract in alloxan induced diabetes in rabbits. *Int J Biomed Adv Res.* 2017; 8: 138-43.
53. Sankaran M. & Vadivel A. Antioxidant and Antidiabetic effect of *Hibiscus rosasinensis* flower extract on Streptozotocin induced experimental rats-a dose response study. *Notulae Scientia Biologicae.* 2011; 3(4): 13-21.
54. Damle M. *Glycyrrhiza glabra* (Liquorice)-a potent medicinal herb. 2014
55. Pastorino G, Cornara L, Soares S, Rodrigues F. Oliveira M. B. P. P. Liquorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*): A phytochemical and pharmacological review. *Phytotherapy Res.*2018; 32(12): 2323–39.
56. Fathima F. & Rajeshkumar S. In Vitro Anti-Diabetic Activity of *Glycyrrhizaglabra*ethanolic Extract. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biol.*2021; 2497-02.
57. Qureshi J. A, Memon Z, Ismail K, Saher F, Motiani V. & Mushtaq Z. Anti-hyperglycemic and anti-dyslipidemic activities of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* root extract in diabetic rats. *J Islamic Int Med College.* 15(2): 98-03.
58. Yang, L, Jiang Y, Zhang Z, Hou J, Tian S. Liu Y. The anti-diabetic activity of licorice, a widely used Chinese herb. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 2020; 263: 113216.
59. Ahmad R, Alqathama A, Aldholmi M, Riaz M, Mukhtar M. H, Aljishi F. et al. Biological screening of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L. from different origins for antidiabetic and anticancer activity. *Pharm.* 16(1): 7.
60. Srivastava J. K, Shankar E. & Gupta S. Chamomile: A herbal medicine of the past with a bright future. *Mol Med Reports.* 2010; 3(6): 895-01.
61. Singh O, Khanam Z, Misra N. & Srivastava M. K. Chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.): an overview. *Pharmacog Rev.* 2011; 5(9): 82.
62. Khan S. S, Najam R, Anser H, Riaz B. & Alam N. Chamomile tea: herbal hypoglycemic alternative for conventional medicine. *Pakistan J Pharm Sci.* 2014; 27.
63. Hajizadeh-Sharafabad F, Varshosaz P, Jafari-Vayghan H, Alizadeh M. & Maleki V. Chamomile (*Matricaria recutita* L.) and diabetes mellitus, current knowledge and the way forward: A systematic review. *Complementary Therap Med.* 2020; 48: 102284.
64. Emam M. A. Comparative evaluation of antidiabetic activity of *Rosmarinus officinalis* L. and Chamomile *recutita* in streptozotocin induced diabetic rats. *Agric. Biol. J Am.* 2012; 3(6): 247-52.
65. Kato A, Minoshima Y, Yamamoto J, Adachi I, Watson A. A. & Nash R. J. Protective effects of dietary chamomile tea on diabetic complications. *J Agri Food Chem.* 2008; 56(17): 8206-11.
66. Shah G, Shri R, Panchal V, Sharma N, Singh B. & Mann A. S. Scientific basis for the therapeutic use of *Cymbopogon citratus*, stapf (Lemon grass). *J Adv Pharm Technol Res.* 2011; 2(1): 3-8.
67. Wifek M, Saeed A, Rehman R, Nisar S. Lemongrass: a review on its botany, properties, applications and active components. *Int J Chem Biochem Sci.* 2016; 9(1): 79-84.
68. Majewska E, Kozłowska M, Gruszczynska-Sekowska E, Kowalska D. & Tarnowska K. Lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) essential oil: extraction, composition, bioactivity and uses for food preservation-a review. *Pol J Food Nutrition Sci.* 2019; 69(4).
69. Mukarram M, Choudhary S, Khan M. A, Poltronieri P, Khan M. M. A, Ali J. et al. Lemongrass essential oil components with antimicrobial and anticancer activities. *Antioxidants.* 2021;11(1): 20.
70. Gunawan-Puteri M. D. P. T, Tjiptadi F. M, Hendra P, Santoso F, Udin Z, Artanti N. et al. Lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) Ethanolic Extract Exhibited Activities That Inhibit glucosidase Enzymes and Postprandial Blood Glucose Elevation. *Makara J Sci.* 2020; 24(4): 217-28.
71. Kassahun T, Girma B, Joshi R. K, Sisay B, Tesfaye K, Taye S. et al. Ethnobotany, traditional use, phytochemistry and pharmacology of *Cymbopogon citratus*. *Int J Herb Med.* 2020; 8: 80-7.
72. Oloyede Omotade&Elekofehinti, Olusola &Akinjiyan, Moses & Ajayi E. & Coker F. &Olabinjo I. Effect of *Cymbopogon citratus* (Lemon grass) on the Expression of Insulin sensitive and Proinflammatory Genes in the Pancreas of Diabetic Rats; 2022.
73. Pattanayak P, Behera P, Das D. & Panda. S. K. *Ocimum sanctum* Linn. A reservoir plant for therapeutic applications: An overview. *Pharmacog Rev.* 2010; 4(7): 95.
74. Verma S. Chemical constituents and pharmacological action of *Ocimum sanctum* (Indian holy basil-Tulsi). *J Phytopharmacol.* 2016; 5(5): 205-7.
75. Raja T . A. R, Reddy R. R. N. &Buchineni M. An evaluation of anti-hyperglycemic activity of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn (leaves) in Wister rats. *The Pharma Innovation.* 2016; 5(1, Part A), 1.

76. Sharma A. D, Kaur I, Angish S, Thakur A, Sania S. & Singh A. Comparative phytochemistry, antioxidant, antidiabetic, and anti-inflammatory activities of traditionally used *Ocimum basilicum* L. *Ocimum gratissimum* L., and *Ocimum tenuiflorum* L. *BioTechnology*. 2022; 103(2): 131.
77. Somasundaram G, Manimekalai K, Salwe K. J. & Pandiamunian J. Evaluation of the antidiabetic effect of *Ocimum sanctum* in type 2 diabetic patients. *Int J Life Sci Pharm Res*; 5: 75-81.
78. Suanarunsawat T, Anantasomboon G. & Piewbang C. Anti-diabetic and anti-oxidative activity of fixed oil extracted from *Ocimum sanctum* L. leaves in diabetic rats. *Exp Therapeutic Med*. 2016; 11(3); 832-40.
79. Islam M. T. Anti-diabetic potential of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn. *Int J Adv Chem Res*. 2022; 6: 38-41.
80. Dwivedi C. & Daspaal S. Antidiabetic herbal drugs and polyherbal formulation used for diabetes: A review. *J Phytopharmacol*. 2013; 2(3): 44-51.

54878478451230606

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **Scopus** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com